

Heterocyclic Fungicides. Part-IV

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Manuscript received 17 March 1980, revised 10 June 1983, accepted 26 November 1983

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one and 3-methyl-4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one are condensed with twelve different 5-monoarylidene-2-mercapto-4-thiazolidones. The products have been characterised by ir spectra and screened for their antifungal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Out of the 24 compounds, 8 showed significant fungicidal activity against both the pathogens. Groups like nitro, benzilidene and cinnamalidene, when attached to the C₅-position of the thiazolidone nucleus improve the fungitoxicity.

THIS is in continuation to our earlier work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁵. It has been observed that 5-pyrazolones and their 4-monobromo derivatives⁶ possess significant fungicidal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Again, 2-mercapto-4-thiazolidones or rhodanines possess insecticidal⁷, pesticidal⁸ and fungicidal⁹ activity. Literature reveals that only a few rhodanines with few substituents at 5-position have been screened for fungicidal activity. On the basis of these observation, it was thought of interest to prepare a number of 5-substituted rhodanines and then condense them with 4-monobromo derivative of 2-pyrazolin-5-one to yield the new compounds.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-mercapto-5'-mono-arylidene-4'-thiazolidone)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (III) was obtained by the condensation of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (II) with 2-mercapto-5-mono-arylidene-4-thiazolidone (I) in 10% ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution. The structure was established from analytical value and ir data. IR spectrum of the condensed product gives the characteristic enolic band at 3010 cm⁻¹ and the >C=O group absorption at 1680 cm⁻¹. The absorption band at 1190 cm⁻¹ is ascribed to >C=S stretching vibration.

R=Ph (Sl. No. 1-12) ; R=H (Sl. No. 13-24).

Fungicidal activity :

All the compounds prepared during the present investigation were assayed for their antifungal activity against the pathogen *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae* by the standard procedure¹⁰ using the spore germination method at various concentrations.

TABLE 1—4-(2'-MERCAPTO-5'-ARYLIDENE-4'-THIAZOLIDONE)-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE

Sl. No.	R ₁	m.p. °C	% inhibition of germination at 1000 ppm	
			<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	C ₆ H ₅	140	58.7	52.4
2.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	115	51.4	59.6
3.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (m)	170	61.3	61.5
4.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	152	54.3	49.6
5.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (o)	175	62.8	54.0
6.	C ₆ H ₄ OH (m)	145	48.0	34.5
7.	C ₆ H ₄ OH (p)	149	45.7	64.6
8.	C ₆ H ₄ OH (o)	101	34.9	36.1
9.	C ₆ H ₄ OHOCH ₃	201	61.8	38.6
10.	C ₆ H ₄ OH=CH	135	59.1	62.5
11.	C ₆ H ₄ N(OH) ₂	180	42.9	39.0
12.	C ₆ H ₅ O	177	31.0	38.7
13.	C ₆ H ₅	187	54.0	57.8
14.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	180	59.2	28.0
15.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (m)	295	44.4	59.6
16.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	190	49.8	58.6
17.	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (o)	220	52.0	56.5
18.	C ₆ H ₄ OH (m)	235	58.0	34.9
19.	C ₆ H ₄ OH (p)	275	49.4	41.5
20.	C ₆ H ₄ OH (o)	210	53.8	44.0
21.	C ₆ H ₄ OHOCH ₃	205	56.9	40.9
22.	C ₆ H ₄ OH=CH	130	63.7	66.0
23.	C ₆ H ₄ N(OH) ₂	192	38.0	37.0
24.	C ₆ H ₅ O	165	48.2	42.0

The yield of these compounds varied between 60 to 80%. All the compounds showed consistent nitrogen analysis.

The fungicidal activity of the 24 synthesised compounds at 1000 ppm concentration is given in

Table 1. Sl. No. 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 13, 17, 22 exhibit significant fungicidal activity against both the pathogens. Sl. No. 4, 9, 14, 18, 20 show good fungicidal activity only against *P. oryzae*. Sl. No. 7, 15, 16 are active only against *H. oryzae*. It has also been found that groups like nitro-benzilidene and cinnamalidene, when attached to the C₅-position of the thiazolidone nucleus improve the fungitoxicity and group like furfuryl at the same position reduces the fungitoxicity against both the pathogens.

Experimental

The melting points of the compounds recorded in Table 1 are uncorrected. 5-Mono-arylidine rhodanine¹¹ and 4-monobromo derivatives of 2-pyrazolin-5-one¹² were prepared by literature methods.

General method for the preparation of 4-(2'-mercapto-5'-monoarylidene-4'-thiazolidone)-2-pyrazolin-5-one: 5-Monoarylidene derivative of 2-mercapto-4-thiazolidone (0.01 mole) was dissolved in ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml) and was added dropwise to a solution of 4-monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) in 10 ml of ethanol. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 4 hr on a water bath, cooled, filtered and acidified with cold dil. HCl. The product thus obtained was washed several times with distilled water, dried and crystallised from ethanol. The compound was soluble in 10%

aqueous alkali and gave red colouration with FeCl₃ solution.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack for carrying out the fungicidal tests and to I. C. A. R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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